

THE EFFECTS OF OXIDATION AND TEMPERATURE ON THE STRENGTH OF CANDIDATE MATERIALS FOR CONTROL RODS IN THE GAS-TURBINE MODULAR HELIUM REACTOR

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ABSTRACT

The feasibility of using carbon-carbon (C/C) composites for high-temperature (1300°C) control rods in the Gas Turbine-Modular Helium Reactor (GT-MHR) is being considered. A conceptual C/C control rod has been designed and the fabrication of prototype components has been demonstrated using existing carbon composite fabrication technology methods. The composite materials employed for the prototype were selected to optimize tolerance to neutron damage. No data, however, were available for the candidate materials on the effects of oxidation nor the potential loss in strength. Preliminary data have recently been obtained.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon-carbon composite materials are currently used in numerous high technology (high temperature) applications including reentry vehicles, exit cones, aircraft brakes, aircraft structural components, and space shuttle nose cones. Today, C/C composite materials are being considered for a high temperature control rod design for the GT-MHR. Control rod materials are exposed to high temperature, neutron irradiation, and helium with its impurities ($O_2 + H_2O + CO + CO_2$). During certain operating events the peak temperature in particular areas of the reactor core can exceed 1300°C, sufficiently high to preclude the insertion of the reference metallic control rods into those areas. Thus the desire to develop high temperature control rods to increase the operating margin of the GT-MHR.

A review [1] of the properties of carbon materials suitable for high-temperature control rods identified several potential graphites. On the other hand, C/C composites offer higher strength and stiffness and perhaps, most significantly, increased fracture toughness. Further, with coatings to control oxidation resistance, C/C composites are expected to have a high strength retention ratio at elevated temperatures.

A conceptual C/C control rod has been designed [2] and prototypic components have been manufactured using existing carbon composite fabrication technology methods. The composite materials employed for the prototype were selected to maximize tolerance to neutron damage and to minimize irradiation-induced dimensional changes. However, no data for the selected

materials were available on the effects of oxidation nor the potential loss in strength due to oxidation. Preliminary data on the effects of oxidation on strength (apparent interlaminar shear strength and flexural strength) of the candidate C/C composite materials for high-temperature control rods have recently been obtained.

MATERIALS

The reference GT-MHR control rod design consists of a number of metal tubular canisters strung on a central metallic spine. Each canister contains neutron absorbing boronated graphite for controlling reactor activity. The conceptual high temperature control rod in Fig. 1 is comprised of three components, all manufactured from C/C composites.

The swivel and connector were machined from a block of orthogonal three-directional (3D) C/C composite. The material was Fiber Materials, Inc. (FMI) type 222 C/C composite, a standard product that is regularly produced for defense applications. The FMI 222 composite is made of Amoco P55 pitch fiber and is pitch impregnated.

The tube elements have a multilayer braided architecture with an integral partial tube closure forming a smooth, spherical radius, and local reinforcement with radial fiber bundles at the open end of the tube for thread strength. The tube construction specifications called for multiple braided layers, Amoco P25 pitch fibers, a tow size of 2000 fibers per bundle, 46% total fiber volume, 90% circumferential-to-axial fiber distribution, 10% radial fibers in the thick section of the tube, pitch impregnation, and 2550°C processing temperature.

British Whitworth (BSW) threads were used to join the control rod components. The BSW thread form was selected because (1) it has a generous root and crown radius that eliminates fiber tearing during machining, and (2) it is relatively coarse, thus maximizing the number of radial fiber bundles in the thread. For the prototype control rod tube the thick section was lengthened to allow additional material for thread strength tests. The swivel is designed to maintain a clearance for free rotational and angular motion of the control rod tube.

EXPERIMENTAL

Test specimens (bend bars), nominally 6.73 mm wide by 50.80 mm long by 6.35 mm thick were machined from the same block of FMI 222 composite used to fabricate the swivels and connectors for the prototypic control rod assembly. The longitudinal axis of the specimens was parallel and perpendicular to the orthogonal axes of the 3D architecture. Further, the longitudinal axis laid in a plane perpendicular to the central axis of the swivels and connectors.

Radial sections were machined from a control rod tube element. These test specimens were 114.3 mm long with a radial cross section having an included angle of 12.5°, resulting in a specimen that was 9.65 mm wide across the face corresponding to the outer surface of the tube element. The thickness of the specimens was 3.18 mm, equivalent to the wall thickness of the tube element. And the specimen length was parallel with the longitudinal axis of the tube element.

To evaluate the effects of oxidation on the strength of the C/C composites, test specimens (FMI 222 and control rod tube element) were exposed to water vapor (2.20 mol %) in helium at 800°C to induce mass losses up to ~5 wt %.

Figure 1. Prototype C/C control rod configuration.

Guidance for conducting bend tests on the C/C composites was obtained from American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) standards: D4762-88, Standard Guide for Testing Automotive/Industrial Composite Materials; D2344, Standard Test Method for Apparent Interlaminar Shear Strength of Parallel Fiber Composites by Short-Beam Method; and D790-92, Standard Test Method for Flexural Properties of Unreinforced and Reinforced Plastics and Electrical Insulating Materials.

It should be noted that ASTM D4762 warns that flexural tests of composites are considered structural tests, not material property tests. Flexural tests of composite materials should not be used for engineering design data, but are useful for quality assurance or comparative properties such as the scoping tests reported here.

Four-point bend tests with a load span of one-half of the support span were conducted on the FMI 222 and tube element specimens. The support span for the interlaminar shear tests was 38.10 mm, whereas the support span for the flexural strength tests was 76.20 mm.

When a beam is loaded in flexure at two central points and supported at two outer points, i.e., four-point bending, the maximum stress in the outer fibers of the beam occurs between the two central loading points that define the load span. This stress may be calculated by the following equation for a load span of one-half of the support span:

$$S = \frac{PLc}{8I}, \quad (1)$$

where

- S = stress in the outer fiber throughout the load span (Pa),
- P = maximum applied load indicated by the testing machine (N),
- L = support span length (m),
- c = distance from the neutral axis to the outer fiber of the beam (m), and
- I = the moment of inertia of the cross section with respect to the neutral axis (m⁴).

For the FMI 222 test specimens which have a rectangular cross section

$$c = d/2 \quad (2)$$

and

$$I = \frac{bd^3}{12}, \quad (3)$$

where

- d = average thickness of the specimen (m), and
- b = average width of the specimen (m).

For the tube element specimens, determination of the values of c and I were more involved. These specimens were tested such that the specimen face corresponding with the outside surface of the tube element was subjected to the maximum tensile loading. The following equations were obtained from Ref. 3:

$$c = R \left[1 - \frac{2 \sin a}{a} \left(1 - \frac{t}{R} + \frac{1}{2-t/R} \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

and

$$I = R^3 t \left(1 - \frac{3t}{2R} + \frac{t^2}{R^2} - \frac{t^3}{4R^3} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$\times \left(a + \sin a \cos a - \frac{2 \sin^2 a}{a} \right)$$

$$+ R^3 t \left[\frac{t^2 \sin^2 a}{3R^2 a (2-t/R)} \left(1 - \frac{t}{R} + \frac{t^2}{6R^2} \right) \right],$$

where

- R = one-half of the outside diameter of the tube element (m),
- t = wall thickness of the tube element (m), and
- a = one-half of the included angle (radians) of the radial section (12.5°).

DISCUSSION

The composite materials employed for the prototype GT-MHR control rod (Fig. 1) were selected to maximize tolerance to neutron damage and to minimize irradiation-induced dimensional changes. Work at Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) on the effect of neutron irradiation on the structure and properties of C/C composite materials [4] has shown that pitch fibers are superior to poly-acrylonitrile (PAN) fibers because of their more crystalline structure. A high final heat treatment (graphitization) temperature is desirable since a more graphitic (crystalline) structure will result. Similarly, a highly crystalline (graphitic) composite matrix is desirable. Therefore, a pitch impregnant was specified in preference to a resin, which yields a nongraphitic glassy carbon matrix. Neutron irradiation-induced shrinkage is more isotropic in 3D-reinforced materials than in two-directional composites. A fine unit cell composite exhibited less dimensional change than a coarse-weave C/C composite. Additionally, 3D-reinforced composites are more isotropic with respect to their mechanical and physical properties. Finally, the strength of C/C composites was found to increase with increasing neutron damage dose.

Hence, pitch fibers, 3D architecture, a fine unit cell, pitch impregnant, and a high heat treatment temperature were specified for the C/C composite components of the GT-MHR prototype control rod. FMI 222 material was selected because (1) it is a 3D pitch fiber pitch impregnated material, (2) it is a standard product, (3) it has a high retention ratio (>90°) for tensile and compressive moduli and strengths [5] in the temperature range of interest, and (4) ORNL has an extensive irradiation data base on the material.

Detailed oxidation studies were carried out in a flowing mixture of water in helium at temperatures up to 1400°C. Above 10% burnoff the activation energy for the oxidation process

in the 3D orthogonal composite was much higher. The associated decrease in oxidation rate was attributed to differences in reactivity between fibers and impregnant. Optical analyses indicated that the pitch fibers were much less reactive than the pitch impregnant. Below 10% burnoff oxidation of the 3D orthogonal composite appeared to correspond to the selective removal of the impregnant. The decrease in density of the composite closely followed the percentage burnoff, and there was no noticeable decrease in geometric volume, suggesting that oxidation through the interior of the test specimens was uniform.

The two control rod composite materials behaved somewhat differently. The impregnant of the braided tube appeared to be less accessible to oxidize than that in the more open 3D orthogonal architecture. Oxidation rates were somewhat lower for the braided architecture. Further, the activation energy after 5% burnoff was nearly equal to that for the 3D orthogonal composite after 10% burnoff.

The deleterious effects of air oxidation on the mechanical properties of graphites [6–8] as well as chopped fiber C/C composites [9] has been demonstrated. Although fibers dominate the mechanical properties of C/C composites, the role of the matrix (impregnant) is not insignificant. The matrix can affect efficient load transfer between fibers. In this study, the selective oxidation of the impregnant resulted in a decrease in the apparent interlaminar shear strength of the orthogonal 3D composite (Fig. 2). Oxidation to 5% burnoff resulted in an ~13% reduction in shear strength.

Multilayer braiding readily lent itself to producing the tubular structure for the prototype control rod. The braided architecture incorporated axially aligned fibers in each layer, producing a pseudo 3D product. The circumferential-to-axial fiber distribution was high, 90%. The tube construction did not contain through-thickness fiber bundles to counteract interlaminar weakness (except in the open end of the tube). Oxidation of the pitch matrix further decreased the apparent interlaminar shear strength (Fig. 3). The flexural strength, on the other hand, was strongly influenced by the architecture. Oxidation of the pitch impregnant appeared to have little effect on flexure strength (Fig. 3). (Data scatter was attributed to severed axial fibers when the control rod tube was machined to the required outside diameter.)

CONCLUSION

An initial prototype C/C composite control rod for the GT-MHR has been designed and fabricated. Initial selection of fibers, composite architectures, and processing details were directed toward minimizing irradiation damage to dimensional stability and strength. Preliminary data on the deleterious effects of oxidation and the potential loss in strength have been obtained.

The successful development of high temperature C/C composite control rods for the GT-MHR will require an integrated approach to the selection of precursor and matrix materials to optimize irradiation resistance, tailoring composite architectures to meet mechanical and thermal property requirements, determining the effects of oxidation, and the selection of coatings to control oxidation resistance.

Figure 2. Strength of 3D orthogonal composite.

Figure 3. Strength of braided composite tube.

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